

Modern strategy of society-nature relations and ecological-legal aspects of natural environment protection

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Abstract: This research explores the complex and dynamic interaction between nature and society in the context of growing anthropogenic pressure on the environment. It analyzes the dependence of human existence on optimal natural conditions and evaluates the consequences of human activities on ecological balance, natural resources, and ecosystem stability. The study emphasizes the need for effective legal, economic, and managerial mechanisms to regulate society–nature relations, highlighting sustainable development, green economy principles, and international cooperation as key directions. Scientific innovation lies in assessing the extent of human influence on natural systems, identifying threats such as resource depletion and environmental degradation, and proposing strategies for ecosystem protection. The findings can be applied in developing environmental policy, improving ecological legislation, and enhancing sustainable resource management in Azerbaijan.

Keywords: *environment, human, society, ecological, development*

Relevance of the topic

One of the global problems of the 20th century is the increasing anthropogenic impact on the environment. Mankind owes its existence to nature. When people did not find what they needed in nature, they created it themselves using natural materials. In material production, labor acts as a means of reproducing nature. Man not only changes the forms of the objects of nature, but also embodies his conscious purpose in those objects. He changes his own nature by influencing nature and changing it. The transformed, productive nature becomes a decisive condition for the future development of man. Although man himself is created from nature, he remains an integral part of nature. At the same time, man always stands against nature as a natural-social force. Nature is a constant, eternal and necessary condition of the production process of material well-being. What nature gives and man takes from it is the basis of production and life. Natural conditions have a decisive influence on the development and location of various areas of production. These conditions either facilitate the development or complicate the development of material production, thereby directly and indirectly affecting the growth of labor productivity. In material production, man appropriates nature for his life. At the same time, spontaneous, local and global processes operate in production. Historically, man studies nature and uses it. Human-made objects and changes in nature are as real and objective as nature's own objects and phenomena. Partial protection of man from the influence of spontaneous forces of nature does not isolate him from nature, on the contrary, it brings him closer and closer to nature, encourages the inclusion of nature in the process of material production more widely. Synthesis of chemical compounds in nature, adaptation of living organisms to polluted environment, etc. an example can be given. The fear of environmental pollution, depletion of natural resources and disruption of the natural ecological balance has created a new form of regulating the interactions between nature and society, which is called nature conservation. In this regard, human activity against the environment is a form of counter-

reaction directed against the activity, the main purpose of which is to regulate the relations between nature and society more effectively with the help of society and the state. Despite all the complexity in the natural sphere, and the lack of the necessary level of natural sciences, scientists have developed a number of basic provisions on the interaction of society and nature, which are of strategic importance for the development of the scientific-methodological basis of ecological law, and those issues are discussed in the dissertation work. Extensive research increases the relevance of the work.

The purpose of the study

— To investigate the impossibility of human existence without the provision of optimal natural conditions;

— To assess the necessity of the effective impact of human activity on the environment;

— To take into account the historical regularity of the interaction of society and nature;

— To determine the economic assessment of the interaction of society and nature;

— To clarify the creation of integration, where nature is a single system, and production operations are social systems within the framework of management and enterprise. If work in the field of nature use is not carried out in a planned and efficient manner, production will inevitably damage the unity and integrity of nature.

— To make wide and efficient use of the legal norms regulating society-nature relations with the aim of protecting, optimizing and improving the environment for the sake of current and future generations.

— To ensure efficient use of International Cooperation and Assistance with the aim of regulating the sustainable use of nature and its resources, environmental protection and management.

1. In order to achieve the set goal, it is necessary to solve the following issues: To satisfy the society's demand for natural resources and to maintain the necessary ecological quality of the environment,

2. To evaluate the system of relations in the process of interaction or influence between society and nature,

3. Develop methods for optimizing the interaction between society and nature, taking into account the interests of future generations,

4. Expansion of international cooperation in the field of efficient use of nature,

5. Formation of legal and organizational conditions for efficient use of nature.

As the natural environment affects productive forces in the interaction of society and nature, it also affected the diversity of economic fields, which played an important role in the dynamic development of society.

Research object

The modern strategy of society-nature relations and ecological-legal assessment of the protection of the quality of the natural environment, the analysis and research of the mutual relations between nature and society are important problems facing modern science and are the scientific-methodical aspects of the dissertation work.

Scientific innovation

On the basis of literary sources, the nature of the mutual relationship between nature and society was investigated, and in order to meet the ever-increasing demands of people in the conditions of the scientific and technical revolution, the areas of expanding their sphere of influence on nature were determined. The nature of human intervention in natural processes, its consequences, legal aspects of protecting ecosystems as a result of sustainable use of resources and ways of cooperation were analyzed.

Research information base and development methods

During the research, the statistical and fund materials of the State Statistics Committee, the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources, the Institute of Geography of the MEA, and numerous literature sources were used. Research methods such as cameral, analytical, statistical, generalization, cartographic, analysis, etc. methods have been applied.

Practical significance of the work

Using the obtained results in the preparation of a modern strategy of society-nature relations, in the evaluation of the positive and negative role of the natural environment in the development of society, in the preparation and legal evaluation of environmental protection measures, in the calculation and forecasting of indicators of sustainable development and development of the green economy in Azerbaijan. to do constitutes the practical importance of the work performed.

Structure and scope of work. The dissertation consists of an introduction, three chapters, conclusions and proposals, and a list of references. The main reasons for the destruction and depletion of ecosystems are as follows:

1. The generation and consumption of food resources in nature occurs according to a waste-free cycle. However, in contrast to this, waste is generated during the production of goods and materials carried out by humans. A person needs 30 tons of raw materials a year to meet his needs, of which 90-95% is waste. In earlier times, natural systems neutralized the waste generated by human activity and could protect themselves from their harmful effects. In modern times, the possibilities of self-cleaning and self-regulation of the biosphere have almost been exhausted.

2. The volume of the natural environment is not enough to process all the waste of human economic activity. Their accumulation poses a threat of global environmental pollution and degradation of natural ecosystems.

3. The resource of mineral resources is gradually running out because it is limited by physical and chemical conditions and the size of our planet.

4. The result of man's destructive activity is long-term and not limited to one generation. In addition, the result of the impact on nature in one area can be reflected far away from it. It's any creates misconceptions about the harmlessness of economic activity (8).

Social stability and sustainability of natural ecosystems are two sides of the same coin. The development of natural and socio-economic systems takes place in accordance with the theory of the complexity of structures and relationships and is ensured by the capacity of the environment. The essence of the theory of complexity is that as the size and complexity of the system organization increases, the energy consumption required to provide this structure and its functions also increases. The amount of energy spent on the further development of the system is gradually decreasing. Further development of the system stops when the input energy equals the amount of energy spent on the stability of the system. The level of development provided under these conditions is called the maximum provision volume of the environment. The supply volume of the environment is the amount of biomass that the ecosystem can provide. The concept of the volume of the natural environment can be explained on such an example. Let's say that 6 gazelles live in 500 ha. Under such conditions, they will increase rapidly and reach 200 within 10 years. At this time, a lot of grass will be used to feed the gazelles. They will destroy their habitat. After that, as a result of various diseases, lack of feed, destruction of the environment, their number will gradually decrease. the process will stabilize when the number of gazelles decreases to 100. As mentioned above, homeostatic mechanisms of self-regulation have been formed in natural systems. Therefore, the volume of the environment is always below the maximum value and overloads do not occur. Sometimes this is also called the "trusted security volume".

As the population and economic prosperity of cities increase, the volume of the environment becomes overloaded, which in turn causes the quality of air and water to decline. As a result, the number of diseases increases, costs are incurred for water and air purification, medical services are provided, etc. In addition, the cost of transportation, utilities, heating and cooling systems, the amount of crime and unemployment in large cities, etc. increases. In other words, as the city grows, the costs of providing its functions increase, while the quality of life decreases. Countries with high population density (Japan, Belgium, Netherlands, etc.) are highly dependent on large areas outside their territory. From this point of view, we are faced

with difficult questions such as estimating the amount of primary natural environment necessary to ensure the current economic development of humanity, developing a strategy for interaction between nature and man, and creating a global development model.

Conclusion and suggestions

1. Scientific and technical progress, socio-economic development, expansion of its application areas, etc., taking place on our planet. caused the emergence and rapid development of new fields of science. The fact that science provides self-development and ensures both the safety and progress of mankind is of special relevance today, which resulted in the emergence of bioethics, which regulates social, legal and ethical aspects.

2. As a result of the environmental crisis that occurred in the second half of the 20th century, the consumerist concept was replaced by a new perspective - humanity's concern about the fate of the biosphere. During this period, pessimists described the pessimistic future of mankind and declared that modern civilization was heading towards destruction. Optimists, on the other hand, believed that based on human consciousness, it would solve environmental problems, and they developed more than a dozen models about the future development of the world. The most important of them was the concept of sustainable development.

3. Since the beginning of the 21st century, environmental problems in the world have become more acute, the reduction of drinking water and food productivity, climate changes, reduction of biodiversity, desertification, pollution, etc. negative processes intensified. The introduction of environmental restrictions led to the formation of a new type of economic development in the world, which was called "green economy". The transition to a green economy will lead to the effective use of natural resources, the preservation and increase of natural capital, the reduction of pollution and greenhouse gases, the preservation of ecosystems and biodiversity, and the increase of income and employment.

4. In recent years, more than twenty national laws and documents related to public health, environmental protection, ecological safety and efficient use of natural resources, rapid development of alternative and renewable energy sources have been adopted in the Republic of Azerbaijan. As a result, the supply of drinking water to the population of the republic has improved, sewage treatment facilities have been put into use, green areas have been built, an action plan for the protection of the Caspian Sea from pollution has been prepared, and the "Azerbaijan 2020: Vision of the Future" Inki-Shaf Concept on sustainable development has been developed.

5. The system of legal norms regulating society-nature social relations with the aim of protection, health and improvement of the natural environment for the sake of present and future human generations is called environmental law. Environmental law is a branch or component of state law. The basis of environmental law is the Constitution and the laws, standards, norms, criminal and administrative punishments adopted on its basis.

6. International cooperation and effective use of international aid is considered the most effective way of sustainable use of natural resources for future generations, protection of the environment from harmful effects, management and regulation of the use of nature. International organizations are mainly financial, technical, informational, consulting, etc. they use such aids.

7. To prevent the depletion and destruction of ecosystems, to maintain the ratio between the volume of the natural environment and the waste resulting from human economic activity, to ensure social stability and the stability of natural ecosystems, taking into account the long-term consequences of destructive human activity.

8. To further intensify the involvement of natural resources in the production cycle by creating favorable conditions for the settlement and activity of society in areas with favorable natural conditions, to substantiate the important role of the interaction of society and nature in the dynamic development of society.

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